

Lesson Study as a Vehicle to Promote and Support Collaborative Professional Development in STEM Education in the Early Years of Primary School

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With increasing focus on primary curricular reform in Ireland, a growing understanding of the importance of education in the early years has led professional development organisations to consider the relevance of STEM (science, technology, engineering and maths) education for young children. This research explores the potential of Lesson Study (LS) as a vehicle to promote and support collaborative professional development in a rural, multi-grade primary school. Three teachers participated in four cycles of LS over the course of one school year. LS was utilised to design and implement integrated STEM lessons in Junior and Senior Infants (ages 4–7 years). Through an action research methodology, qualitative data were generated from interviews, lesson plans, weekly collaborative meetings, observation sheets, and the researcher’s reflective journal and field notes. Analysis suggests that teachers began to develop new pedagogical practices as a result of iterative and collaborative LS processes. Findings also reveal insights into the knowledge-related demands of designing and implementing STEM lessons. Successive and collaborative cycles enabled teachers to become more confident in their teaching of STEM education, and they believed they had a greater understanding of the children’s learning. While teachers perceived LS to be a beneficial form of professional development, some factors constrained their engagement, including practical, cultural and sustainability challenges. The work concludes by contemplating the place of LS and STEM education in the current educational landscape and makes recommendations to support their implementation nationally.

Introduction

Internationally, Lesson Study (LS) has been recognised as an effective model of professional development to support curriculum reform (Lewis & Takahashi, 2013) and the provision of high-quality mathematics experiences to young learners (Leavy & Hourigan, 2017). Presently in Ireland, the proposed inclusion of ‘Mathematics, Science and Technology Education’ as one of the five broad curricular areas within the draft primary curriculum framework (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2020) offers an opportunity to provide professional development that introduces new teaching, learning, and assessment approaches that enhance STEM education. Accordingly, this study explores the reality of implementing integrated STEM practices in an infant classroom where LS was used as a form of professional development. This research examines and assesses LS as a tool to support teachers in developing their knowledge and skills in teaching STEM in the early years. The findings of this study are timely as the Irish STEM policy is in the early stages of implementation; therefore, this research can inform policy makers, teacher educators, schools and teachers concerning the constraining and enabling factors that may exist whilst attempting to implement change in Irish primary schools’ STEM practices.

Literature Review

Lesson Study

LS originated as a practice in Japan in the late 1800s and has been the primary vehicle for Japanese teachers' professional development. LS integrates many of the features of effective professional development (Vermunt, Vrikki, Warwick, Mercer, & van Halem, 2019; Hourigan & Leavy, 2019; 2021). Desirable outcomes associated with LS include development of teacher knowledge (Cajkler, Wood, Norton, Pedder, & Xu, 2015; Leavy & Hourigan, 2018a; Ní Shúilleabháin, 2016; Dudley, Xu, Vermunt, & Lang, 2019), an increased focus on children's learning (Cajkler et al. 2015; Leavy & Hourigan, 2018b; Dudley et al. 2019; Vermunt et al. 2019), increased teacher collaboration (Lewis, Perry, & Hurd, 2009, Murata, 2011, Cajkler et al. 2015, Hourigan and Leavy 2021) and reduced feelings of professional isolation (Lewis et al. 2009, Cajkler et al. 2015).

Different forms of LS have developed as it has been adopted and adapted in different countries (Murata, 2011). However, numerous challenges to LS have been cited concerning the cultural contexts of settings and the structure of schools. Obstacles to LS include the cost of implementation, sustainability, insufficient teacher content knowledge and connection to student learning, teachers' lack of familiarity with the research process, teachers' already hectic work schedules, lack of solid leadership, extra stress for teachers to refine their practice, and problems in collaboration (Murata, 2011; Akiba & Wilkinson, 2016; Wolthuis, van Veen, de Vries, & Hubers, 2020; Hourigan and Leavy, 2021). Considering the various barriers schools face in adopting and adapting LS, it is unsurprising that its sustainability has been challenging in some countries. Murata (2011) adds that teachers are not accustomed to professional development being sustained from year to year; she believes that teachers may practise LS for one year and then expect to move on to their next professional development experience. Wolthuis et al. (2020) found that the LS process was too time-consuming for what it yielded: "one lesson plan or a one-time insight into student responses" (p. 10). They believe that if long-term, school-based professional development is to become the norm, a cultural shift is required involving teachers changing their perspective on professional development.

STEM Education

Recent literature reports many advantages to young children learning through STEM education (Clements & Sarama, 2016; Rosicka, 2016) and the importance of early exposure to build positive learning dispositions (Park, Dimitrov, Patterson, & Park, 2017). In Ireland, the STEM Education Policy Statement (2017–2026) recognises the importance of introducing STEM in early years education, "We need a national focus on STEM education in our early years settings and schools to ensure we have an engaged society and a highly-skilled workforce in place" (Department of Education and Skills 2017, p. 5). The influential role of primary teachers is highlighted "as the primary educators at the foundation of the STEM pipeline, it is critical that those involved in STEM policy, curricula and teacher education are cognisant of their role of influence" (Hourigan, Dwyer, Leavy, & Corry, 2021, p. 20).

Teachers' perceptions of STEM are critical, as they influence the time and consideration given to STEM education (Simoncini & Lasen, 2018).

The literature reveals several issues that may impact on the quality of STEM teaching and learning, notably, teacher competence and confidence, inquiry-based learning, content and pedagogic knowledge (Honey, Pearson & Schweingruber, 2014). Further inconsistency and confusion are evident in the many definitions of STEM education and the many interpretations of the integration of science, technology, engineering and maths (Honey et al. 2014; Margot & Kettler, 2019; Hourigan et al. 2021). With these numerous challenges in mind, research highlights the need for collaborative, sustained and situated STEM professional development (Honey et al. 2014; Rosicka, 2016; MacCraith, 2016; Hourigan et al. 2021).

Data Collection

This study was conducted in two rural schools over an eight-month period; within the researcher's own infant classroom (School 1) and a second rural infant classroom in a neighbouring school (School 2). The LS group consisted of the researcher (B.F.), two other Special Education Teachers (SETs) and a More Knowledgeable Other (M.K.O.) in the final LS cycle. Two semi-structured interviews were conducted with both SETs at the beginning and end of the research and one semi-structured interview conducted with the principal at the end of the study. The interviews captured the value that teachers placed on LS and LS's feasibility as a vehicle of professional development. Collaborative LS group meetings were conducted weekly throughout the research process. Collaborative lesson plans and observation schedules were designed and followed by the participants for each research lesson.

Findings

The most pervasive theme revealed by the data was that the teachers highly valued the professional collaboration inherent in LS. LS created a stronger community of teachers, broke down professional isolation and created learning opportunities. This research supports findings from Dudley (2013) that LS is a vehicle for collaboration to enhance professional capital (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012). Teachers recognised that creating an atmosphere of openness enabled them to share challenges of practice and provide solutions. Empowering leadership to nurture colleagues' collective capacity and the distribution of leadership also provided a foundation upon which LS grew.

This research suggests that LS effectively brought about positive changes in teacher practice (Corcoran, 2011; Dudley, 2013; Cajkler et al. 2015; Hourigan & Leavy, 2021). Teachers began to remove themselves from being the sole transmitters of knowledge to facilitating discussion during STEM lessons. However, this shift in practice proved challenging for some participants and this echoes findings from Margot and Kettler (2019). LS provided support to take pedagogical risks and trial new teaching approaches. However, teachers require time to engage with the meaning of inquiry-based education and their role as facilitator.

Implementing STEM education for the first time extended teachers' Subject Matter Knowledge (Shulman, 1986) and Pedagogic Content Knowledge (ibid) in how to design, deliver and teach STEM lessons, and notice how children work. Collaborative planning and reflection aided teachers in solving problems and finding new levels of understanding when grappling with STEM, thus aligning with research by Murata (2011) and Vermunt et al. (2019). Engineering was regarded as a linchpin that successfully drew the other disciplines together in a more meaningful manner. Teachers observed that Aistear (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2009) supported STEM learning, in particular promoting targeted language development and positive learning dispositions.

LS enabled a sharper focus on children's learning during STEM lessons. Dudley (2013) believes that LS helps teachers subdue the classroom's intricacies, leading them to observe children anew. By observing the children's learning, teachers became more responsive to various children's needs and pitched lessons more appropriately. The children exhibited 21st century-skill development, positive learning dispositions and impressive engagement, which together demonstrate how powerful early STEM experiences can be.

Many factors affected teachers' participation in LS. International research (Murata 2011; Akiba & Wilkinson 2016; Wolthuis et al. 2020) has detailed the challenges of implementing LS outside of Japan; similar challenges were recognised in this study. There were practical challenges to implementing LS in the primary school system. Cultural challenges were evident, as LS was unlike any professional development that teachers had undertaken previously. Lastly, the sustainability of LS remains an area for further support and study.

Conclusion

Although this was a small-scale study, it provides important insights into LS's introduction in an Irish primary school. Additionally, it provides interesting understandings into the challenges faced by teachers when introducing STEM education in primary school. LS provided a context for teachers to introduce STEM education to Junior and Senior Infants. LS was a new form of professional development for the teachers and time is required for teachers to become familiar with the process. This experience of professional development may have been a stimulus for teachers to recognise that an alternative approach is possible. The positive outcomes of the research justify the conclusion that LS could be adapted for use in Irish primary schools.

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